

A SYSTEM OF MEASURES TO REDUCE THE HEALTH RISK TO PEOPLE LIVING IN THE AREA OF IMPACT OF ADVERSE PRODUCTION FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

The increasing man-made impact on the environment necessitates the development and improvement of measures to reduce the risk of adverse factors affecting public health. Currently, the solution to this problem is based on the development of public health risk assessment methodologies and the creation of effective information and analytical systems for social and hygienic monitoring. Among the diverse adverse environmental factors, chemical factors—the impact of man-made pollutants on the human body—are of significant importance. Therefore, it is necessary to assess both the total chemical load on the human body and its individual components, resulting in aggregated and cumulative risks.

Relevance of the work. The increasing man-made impact on the environment necessitates the development and improvement of measures to reduce the risk of adverse factors affecting public health. Currently, the solution to this problem is based on the development of public health risk assessment methodologies and the creation of effective information and analytical systems for social and hygienic monitoring. Among the diverse adverse environmental factors, chemical factors—the impact of man-made pollutants on the human body—are of significant importance. Therefore, it is necessary to assess both the total chemical load on the human body and its individual components, resulting in aggregated and cumulative risks.

Tire production is a leading industry and significantly contributes to the human-caused impact on the environment. The International Agency for Research on Cancer has listed rubber and tire industries as hazardous carcinogens. The tire rubber manufacturing process involves the use of substances containing carcinogenic impurities. Tire dust has been found to contain over 140 chemical compounds of varying toxicity. Polyaromatic hydrocarbons and volatile carcinogens such as N-nitrosamines are particularly hazardous to human health.

The current stage of hygiene development requires the use of more sophisticated methodological approaches and technologies to address the complex challenges facing hygiene science and practice. In recent years, probabilistic methods for assessing carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic health risks have been applied to assessing the impact of environmental factors on public health and to justify preventive and health-improving measures, and a corresponding regulatory and methodological framework has been

developed. Moreover, these methods have been repeatedly tested and can be effectively applied both for large-scale assessments of the situation in a given territory as part of a social and hygiene monitoring system and for assessing the public health risk posed by exposure to unfavorable factors at specific industries.

Regional studies have shown that air pollution is the primary adverse factor in terms of dose exposure and biological effects on the health of the Tashkent population. It has been established that the Amtel-Chernozemye Tire Complex OJSC ranks among the leading industrial enterprises in Voronezh in terms of pollutant emissions.

In Tashkent, the tire plant is located within the city limits, with residential areas located a short distance from the facility. In accordance with SanPiN 2.2.1/2.1.1.1200-03, the standard sanitary protection zone for this type of natural resource is 300 meters.

The production process is constantly being improved. Recent changes to the process included the introduction of high-performance Type P passenger car and light truck tires with rim diameters ranging from 14 to 21 speed categories. Producing high-quality tires with consistent performance in the new facility places greater demands on the physical and mechanical properties of rubber compounds, the cord processing process, compliance with specified tolerances, the linear dimensions of tire components, their geometry and weight, and the precision of assembly and vulcanization processes. These changes have resulted in changes in the volume and range of pollutants emitted into the atmosphere. This necessitated a reassessment of the contribution of air pollutants to the health risks and actual morbidity of the population living in areas exposed to adverse factors in the tire industry.

The study was conducted within the framework of the industry research program "Hygienic Safety of Uzbekistan: Problems and Solutions (2020-2025)".

The aim of the work: scientific substantiation of a system of preventive measures to reduce the risk to public health caused by the impact of pollutant emissions into the atmosphere from tire production.

Research objectives

1. Provide a comprehensive hygienic assessment of the anthropogenic load on the environment in the area of Uzbekistan.
2. Conduct an assessment of the risk to public health caused by exposure to air pollution from emissions, and identify priority pollutants that make the greatest contribution to carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic risk.
3. To identify the relationship between the level of airborne anthropogenic load and the incidence of diseases in different age groups of the population (children under 14 years of age and adults) living in the zone of influence of emissions.

Study results. The leading factor contributing to the complex anthropogenic load (CN = 17.06) in the tire manufacturing area is air pollution (averaging 10.1 ± 0.97 units over the long-term period). Air quality monitoring indicates that atmospheric air levels exceed hygienic standards for nitrogen dioxide by 1.12 times, manganese and its compounds by 1.42 times, sulfur dioxide by 1.52 times, formaldehyde by 1.66 times, and suspended solids by 1.59 times. The priority pollutants of the ground layer of atmospheric air, the total contribution of which to the gross emission is 95%, include 15 ingredients, including butane (30.3%), petroleum gasoline (20.3%), carbon monoxide (11.1%), sulfur dioxide (8.4%), soot (3.7%), as

well as 9 carcinogens (benzo (a) pyrene , petroleum gasoline, benzene, 1,3-butadiene, styrene, soot, lead, formaldehyde and ethylbenzene), the content of which in the ground layer, according to modeling data, does not exceed the MAC p for the air of populated areas.

The total individual carcinogenic risk to population health caused by exposure to atmospheric emissions from tire production in areas located at a distance of 500 m to 4.9 km from the source is from $4.7 \cdot 10^{-9}$ to $9.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$, which belongs to the second risk range (more than $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$, but less than $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$) and corresponds to the maximum permissible risk, the level of which is subject to constant monitoring. The greatest contribution to the total individual carcinogenic risk is made by emissions of gasoline (43.9 - 70.8%), styrene (0.5-55.6%), benzene (0.2-25.4%), and soot (0.1-3.2%).

The non-carcinogenic risk, characterized by the total hazard indices (HI) at the boundary of the designed sanitary protection zone, exceeds the permissible level (one unit) at three of the nineteen control points under consideration, ranging from 1.1 to 2.0 units. The largest contributions to the total non-carcinogenic risk at the control points are made by inorganic dust (31-96%) and kerosene (38%). With unidirectional chronic inhalation exposure to critical organs and systems, a high hazard index was noted for a group of substances affecting the respiratory system at one control point of the designed sanitary protection zone (HI = 1.4), based on the existing situation.

The information basis for developing measures to reduce the health risks associated with the impact of pollutant emissions into the atmosphere from tire production is a combined analysis of the state of the environment and modeling data on pollutant concentrations in the ground layer of air, the identification of priority risk factors, relationships, patterns, and a forecast of the development of the situation in the system "level of technogenic load - population morbidity."

The effectiveness of the sanitary-technical and technological measures implemented at the enterprise is confirmed by a decrease in the actual volume of emissions over a 7-year period by 2.5 times, over the last year - by 10%, as well as the current absence of excess concentrations of harmful substances, including by summation groups (according to modeling and laboratory control data) at the control points of the regulatory sanitary protection zone, in residential buildings, and at the boundary of the designed sanitary protection zone, taking into account the background, the individual carcinogenic risk is at an acceptable level (less than 10^{-4}).

Conclusions: The incidence rate of children living in areas with high levels of air pollution (maximum up to 18.0 units) near the location of tire production is significantly higher than the incidence rate of a relatively clean area both in terms of overall incidence of children ($T_r = 17.02 > T_{table} = 2.262$ at $p < 0.05$) and in terms of respiratory diseases ($T_r = 11.69 > T_{table} = 2.262$ at $p < 0.05$), including asthma ($T_{rasc} = 4.23 > T_{taCl} = 2.262$ at $p < 0.05$), pneumonia ($T_{raCl} = 8.63 > T_{taCl} = 2.262$ at $p < 0.05$). Positive statistically significant correlations were revealed between the indicators of total air pollution and the incidence of asthma in children, asthmatic status, endocrine diseases, and congenital malformations ($r = 0.33-0.64$, $p < 0.05$).

Reliable differences in the incidence rates of the adult population in the area with a high level of aerotechnogenic load in relation to the relatively clean area are observed less frequently than in children and were identified for diseases of the endocrine system, respiratory organs and congenital malformations ($T_{\text{trac}} = 2.57 - 4.25 < T_{\text{table}} \wedge 2.262$, at $p < 0.05$).

List of references:

1. Abduraimovna, A.D., Turg'unboyevna, Y.N. and Rustamovna, Q.S., 2023. QIZLARNI OILA VA JAMIYATDA O'ZO'RNINI TOPISHDA PSIXOLOGIK KO'NIKMA VA MA'NAVIY YETUKLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(7), pp.310-313.
2. ERMATOV, N., KASSYMOVA, G., TAJIYEVA, K., KHASANOVA, M., ALIMUKHAMEDOVA, M., & AZIMOVA, S. (2020). Expression of tissue-specific genes in mice with hepatocarcinogenesis. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* (09752366), 12(3).
3. Ikramova, N. A., Jalolov, N. N., Mirsagatova, M. R., Kasimova, K. T., Sadirova, M. K., & Sul'tonov, E. Y. (2025, April). AMBIENT TEMPERATURE AND THE RISK OF THERMOREGULATORY DISORDERS AMONG TRAFFIC POLICE OFFICERS: AN EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS. *International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education*.
4. Ikramova, N. A., Mirsagatova, M. R., Jalolov, N. N., Kasimova, K. T., Sul'tonov, E. Y., & Sadirova, M. K. (2025, April). THE EFFECT OF THERMAL LOAD ON THE BODY OF OUTDOOR WORKERS: ANALYSIS BASED ON MEDICAL AND HYGIENIC INDICATORS. *International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education*.
5. Kamilova, D. N., Saydalikhujaeva, S. K., Abdashimov, Z. B., Rakhmatullaeva, D. M., & Tadjieva, X. S. (2021). Employment relations and responsibilities of medical institutions workers in a pandemic in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Medicine and Innovations*, 2(13-1).
6. Kamilova, D. N., Saydalikhujaeva, S. K., Rakhmatullaeva, D. M., Makhmudova, M. K., & Tadjieva, K. S. (2021). Professional image of a teacher and a doctor. *British Medical Journal*, 1(4), 4-14.
7. Masharipova, R. Y., & Khasanova, G. M. (2020). Improvement of motor fitness of dental students in the process of physical education classes. *Bulletin of Science*, 5(3), 101-104.
8. Masharipova, R., Togaynazarov, S., Pakhrudinova, N., Khasanova, G., & Abdurahimov, B. (2020). The main factors of formation and physical culture in society. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(12).
9. Qosimova, X. T., Ikramova, N. A., Juraboyeva, D. N., & Mukhtorova, D. A. (2025, March). THE ADVERSE EFFECTS OF SMARTPHONES ON COGNITIVE ACTIVITY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AND WAYS TO MITIGATE THEM. In *The Conference Hub* (pp. 76-79).
10. Sadullayeva, X. A., Salomova, F. I., & Sul'tonov, E. Y. (2023). Ochiq suv havzalari muhofazalash ob'ekti sifatida. In *V международная научно-практическая конференция «Современные достижения и перспективы развития охраны здоровья населения»*.
11. Sadullayeva, X. A., Salomova, F. I., Mirsagatova, M. R., & Kobiljonova Sh, R. (2023). Problems of Pollution of Reservoirs in the Conditions of Uzbekistan.
12. Salomova, F. I., & Kosimova, H. T. (2017). RELEVANCE OF STUDYING INFLUENCE OF THE BONDS OF NITROGEN POLLUTING THE ENVIRONMENT ON HEALTH OF THE POPULATION SUFFERING CARDIOVASCULAR ILLNESSES (REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN). In

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION (pp. 81-83).

13. Salomova, F. I., Ahmadaliev, N. O., Sadullaeva, K. A., & Sherkuzieva, G. F. (2022). Dust storm and atmosphere air pollution in Uzbekistan.
14. Saydalikhujaeva, S. K., & Rustamova, H. Y. (2022). Motivation and satisfaction with the professional activities of nurses anesthetists. *MedUnion*, (1), 163-169.
15. Saydalikhujayeva, S. K., Kosimova, K. T., Mamadzhonov, N. A., & Ibragimova, S. R. (2020). The role of modern pedagogical technologies in improving the system of higher medical education in the republic of Uzbekistan. *New Day in Medicine*, 1(29), 85.
16. ShR, K., Mirrakhimova, M. H., & Sadullaeva, H. A. (2022). Prevalence and risk factors of bronchial asthma in children. *Journal of Theoretical and Clinical Medicine*, 2, 51-56.
17. Tadjieva, K. S. (2024). USING SITUATIONAL TASKS TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING MEDICAL CHEMISTRY. *Web of Teachers: Inderscience Research*, 2(1), 64-68.
18. Tadjieva, K. S., Kosimova, K. T., & Niyazova, O. A. (2025). THE ROLE OF AIR POLLUTION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES.
19. Tursunov, D., Sabiorva, R., Kasimova, X., Azizova, N., & Najmiddinova, N. (2016). Status of oxidant and antioxidant systems in alloxan diabetes and ways its correction. In *Science and practice: a new level of integration in the modern world* (pp. 188-190).
20. АБДУЛЛАЕВА, М., & ТАДЖИЕВА, Х. (2023). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ РАСТВОРИМОСТИ СИСТЕМ: КАЛИЕВАЯ СОЛЬ-ОДНОЗАМЕЩЕННЫЙ УКСУСНОКИСЛЫЙ МОНОЭТАНОЛАММОНИЙ-ВОДА. *Международный центр научного партнерства «Новая Наука»(ИП Ивановская ИИ) КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ: НАУЧНЫЙ ДЕБЮТ 2023 Петрозаводск, 03 декабря 2023 года Организаторы: Международный центр научного партнерства «Новая Наука»(ИП Ивановская ИИ).*
21. Акромов, Д. А., & Касимова, Х. Т. (2017). Результаты изучения токсикологических свойств фунгицида "Вербактин". *Молодой ученый*, (1-2), 2-3.
22. Ахмадалиева, С. У., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. ОСНОВЫ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ СТУДЕНТА МЕДИКА. ББК: 51.1 л0я43 С-56 А-95, 228.
23. Балтабаев, У. А., Джураев, А. Д., & Таджиева, Х. С. (2008). Реакции фенилизотиоцианата с α -аминокислотами. *Жур. Химия и химическая технология*, 1, 39-42.
24. Денисова, У. Ж., & Ахмадалиева, С. У. (2019). МЕТОДЫ, ПОВЫШАЮЩИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ СТУДЕНТОВ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. In *ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 141-143).
25. Денисова, У. Ж., & Машарипова, Р. Ю. (2019). Изучение взаимосвязи между морфометрическими характеристиками телосложения баскетболисток 16-18 лет и показателями физической подготовленности. *Вестник науки*, 5(12), 17-22.